

EXAMINATION OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL PERFORMANCES OF THE CANDIDATES ENTERING THE SPORTS TESTS IN POLICE VOCATIONAL EDUCATION CENTERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to examine the psychological performance levels of applicants, who prepared for sports tests in Police Vocational Education Centers in Kayseri. 427 applicants, who have been randomly selected, have voluntarily participated in the research. As data collection tools for the research, the Psychological performance Scale which was developed by Loehr J.E. and the Personal Information Form which was prepared by the researcher have been applied. The obtained data has been statistically analyzed via SPSS20.0 package program. The personal information of the applicants and the total score of inventory and total factor scores (f) and percent value have been determined and shown. To compare them with regarding gender the statistics of Mann-Whitney U test have been applied while statistical outputs of Kruskal Wallis test have been applied in order to make comparison with considering their Public Personnel Selection Examination (PPSE) scores, departments that they graduated, educational status of their parents and neighborhoods where they live. As a result of the statistical analyses; when the psychological performance levels of the applicants have been examined, there is no statistically significant difference in accordance with gender while there are statistically significant differences in accordance with (PPSE) scores, departments that they graduated, educational status of their parents and neighborhoods/residences where they live. Consequently, with considering psychological performance of applicants who prepare for sports tests of police vocational training centers it has been expected to contribute to making right choices. Policing is a profession in which the profession requires physical toughness as well as psychological performance. Therefore, in the entrance exams for police vocational education centers, applying psychological performance and psychological tests in addition to sports tests should be considered.

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1. Introduction

"Police" as legally defined; *"is an armed executive and regulatory power that fulfills the duties given by the codes and regulations, helps children, disabled and weak people who need help, secures public peace, activity and process security of individuals and public; immunity of residence, protection for people's lives, properties and honor"*. It is very important to raise the quality of the police department that performs similar duties in our country and ensure that it is renewed from day to day. In order to improve the performance of the Turkish police and to reveal the areas requiring reform, it is necessary to take the police service on a global scale (Barley, 1999). In Turkey, the renewal plays a major role in the police's professional culture to reach the desired police behaviors and attitudes (Yılmaz, 2004). It is known that the Turkish Police Service is a giant public institution with the central and provincial organizations of the General Directorate of Security Affairs. The whole of the services that this institution fulfills is related to social life (Kahraman & Durmaz, 2004). The inadequacy of the program development studies within the police basic education, the large number of classes, not being able to select the suitable candidates, and the limitations on the financial resources allocated for training are very controversial issues. It is clear that police schools have an educational, theory, and general literature-based structure rather than a teaching, practice, and subject-oriented structure. For this reason, it seems that graduates often express the sense of dissatisfaction they experience when they start their professional life as a service member as *"the school and the service are totally different"* or *"I did not learn any of these at school"* (Babacan, 2011). If the applicant is deemed to be sufficient after evaluating his/her physical appearance, physical strength, correctness of his/her conversation, his/her level of self-esteem, representation ability, understanding and expression skills, the candidate is determined as "Police High School Student Candidate" by the Candidate Evaluation and Selection Board established at the relevant police school (Güloğlu, 2003).

Situations such as irregular working hours, encountering/confronting crime, criminals and people at the terminal points of life, working in an environment where conflict and tensions can often arise, the organization's specific characteristics (efficiency, authority, danger), frequent appointments, limitations on social life, working at holidays, the people's point of view on police, obtaining unlawful profit have psychologically and physically affected the police (Findıklı, 2001). Because of the stress factors in the police profession, the police officers may be at risk in terms of various personal and psychological health concerns (Karaffa & Koch, 2015). In terms of coping with negative attitudes, the police organization should do more to address mental health-related processes at the individual and institutional level (Loher, 1986). Under these circumstances, as well as physical characteristics, the psychological characteristics have also become an indispensable component for being a police. Psychological performance that has numerous definitions in written sources includes

concepts such as coping with pressure in an effective way, being psychologically strong (Bababcan, 2011), being committed, high concentration skill, high level resoluteness and a robust sense of self (Güloğlu, 2003). In other words, psychological performance can be expressed in the form of positive psychological capacity that can be improved to restore self and to get back in some negative circumstances such as adversity, failure, conflict and increased responsibility (Fındıklı, 2001). Measuring psychological performance is a crucial factor for evaluating and developing psychological performance (Karaffa & Koch, 2015). Psychological performance, as well as being associated with positive outcomes in particular areas can potentially protect young people from risky or harmful behavior interpersonal relations (Loher, 1986). Although there are certain studies regarding the police profession, the number of studies related to the evaluation of police candidates is very few in the literature. In the entrance exams for the police service, verbal and physical performance tests as well as evaluating the psychological status of police officers are considered to be useful. The purpose of our article is to contribute to the literature studies on psychological performance by creating awareness of the more comprehensive consideration of candidates that are going to be the performers of the policing profession.

2. Material and Method

2.1 Studying Group

This research is in the relational screening model. This screening model can be defined as "*... research models aimed at determining the presence and/or degree of alteration between two and more variables*" (Karasar, 2007). Since an assessment will be carried out in order to determine the psychological performance level and demographic characteristics of applicants who were getting prepared for sports tests in Police Vocational Education Centers in Kayseri, the research is a descriptive study.

2.2 Data Collection Tools

Psychological performance scale and socio demographic information form were applied as data collection tools. Before the forms were applied, the candidates were provided with a comfortable environment and the scales were applied in a face-to-face manner after the academicians informed the candidates about the study

2.3 Establishment of Voluntary Groups

In the years 2017 and 2018, 10,000 candidates will be admitted to the police schools across Turkey. A total of 427 individuals selected randomly among 650 candidates who actively participate in policing courses in Kayseri province.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

	Variables	N	%
Gender	Male	215	50.4
	Female	212	49.6
Age	22-23	54	12.6
	24-25	225	52.7
	26-27	148	34.7
Residence	Town	18	24.5
	Province	171	25.2
	District	46	25.7
	Metropolis	192	24.5
Educational Status of Mother	Elementary School	203	47.5
	High School	27	29.7
	Associate degree	62	14.5
	University	35	8.2
Educational Status of Father	Elementary School	176	41.2
	High School	166	38.9
	Associate degree	49	11.5
	University	36	8.4
Department	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	9.6
	Faculty of Education	65	15.2
	Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences	52	12.2
	Faculty of Science	33	7.7
	Faculty of Literature	50	11.7
	Applied Sciences	21	4.9
	Faculty of Health Sciences	35	8.2
	Faculty of Theology	41	9.6
	Faculty of Engineering	50	11.7
Faculty of Communication	39	9.1	

2.4 Socio-Demographic Information Form

The socio demographic information form contains 6 questions in order to obtain information about the participants' age, gender, and department that they graduated from, educational status of parents and residence address.

2.5 Psychological Performance Scale

The Psychological Performance Inventory (PPI), which was developed by Loehr J. E. and introduces the profile of the athlete's psychological skills, was used in the study. The answer choices of inventory that was prepared according to closed-end question type 5-point Likert scale are "always", "frequently", "sometimes", "seldom" and "never" (Loher, 1986). The studies for adapting PPI to Turkish language have been carried out. The internal consistency coefficient "Cronbach Alpha" for the Turkish version of the scale has been found as 0.70 for self-confidence, 0.63 for negative energy, 0.43 for attention control, 0.53 for visualization, 0.62 for imaging control, 0.53 for positive energy, and 0.65 for attitude control (p <0, 01) Perry, Clough, Crust, Earle & Nicholls, 2013).

2.6 Analysis of the Data

The scores achieved in the study were coded and entered into the SPSS 20.0 package program and analyzes were made through this program. Kolmogrov Smirnov test statistics were applied to examine the distributions of the obtained data and it was determined that the distributions of the data were not normal. Therefore, non-parametric analyzes were applied to the obtained data. Mann-Whitney U test statistics were used in the comparisons according to gender, Kruskal Wallis test statistics were used in comparisons according to ages, graduated departments, education levels of mother and father and living conditions

3. Findings

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of students' responses to the questions of the questionnaire

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean ± SD
Self-confidence	427	6.00	25.00	13.45±4.86
Negative Energy	427	8.00	26.00	16.39±3.73
Attention Control	427	9.00	25.00	16.80±3.27
Visualization	427	6.00	24.00	13.33±3.97
Motivation Level	427	6.00	25.00	13.34±4.23
Positive Energy	427	6.00	25.00	15.08±3.80
Attitude Control	427	6.00	25.00	12.55±3.89
Psychological performance Total	427	55	151	100.96±21.63

As seen in Table 2, the mean score of the self-confidence of the applicants is 13.45, the mean score of the negative energy is 13.45, the mean score of the attention control is 16.80, the mean score of the visualization is 13.33, the mean score of the motivation level is 13.34, the score of the positive energy is 15.08, mean score of attitude control is 12.55 and mean score of total psychological performance total is 100.96.

Table 3: Evaluation of Participants' Psychological performance by Gender

	Gender	N	Median (25-75)	Z	P
Self-confidence	Male	215	13.00 (10.00-17.00)	-0.91	.928
	Female	212	12.00 (10.00-17.00)		
Negative Energy	Male	215	16.00 (14.00-19.00)	-1.42	.887
	Female	212	16.00 (13.00-17.00)		
Attention Control	Male	215	17.00 (15.00-19.00)	-1.034	.301
	Female	212	17.00 (15.00-19.00)		
Visualization	Male	215	14.00 (10.00-17.00)	-.700	.484
	Female	212	13.00 (10.00-16.00)		
Motivation Level	Male	215	14.00 (10.00-16.00)	-.773	.440
	Female	212	13.00 (10.00-16.00)		
Positive Energy	Male	215	15.00 (12.00-17.00)	-1.561	.118
	Female	212	15.00 (13.00-17.00)		
Attitude Control	Male	215	13.00 (10.00-15.00)	-0.53	.958
	Female	212	12.00 (10.00-15.00)		
Psychological performance Total	Male	215	102.00 (85.00-116.00)	-.253	.801
	Female	212	100.00 (87.00-116.57)		

p < 0.005

When Table 3 is examined, it is seen that there is no significant difference between the gender variable of the participants and the sub-dimensions of self-confidence, negative energy, attention control, visualization, motivation level, positive energy and attitude control. On the other hand, there was also no significant relationship between total score of psychological performance and gender variable.

Table 4: Evaluation of Participants' Psychological performances by Age

	Age Groups	N	Median (25-75)	X ²	P	U
Self-confidence	22-23	54	12.00 (10.00-15.75)	27.813	.000*	26/27
	24-25	225	14.00 (11.00-19.00)			24/25
	26-27	148	10.00 (10.00-15.00)			
Negative Energy	22-23	54	16.00 (15.00-18.00)	7.015	.030	-
	24-25	225	17.00 (13.00-20.00)			
	26-27	148	16.00 (13.00-18.75)			
Attention Control	22-23	54	16.00 (14.00-19.00)	32.585	.000*	26/27
	24-25	225	18.00 (16.00-20.00)			24/25
	26-27	148	16.00 (14.00-18.00)			22/23 24/25
Visualization	22-23	54	12.00 (10.00-15.00)	.608	.738	-
	24-25	225	14.00 (10.00-17.00)			
	26-27	148	14.00 (11.00-16.00)			
Motivation Level	22-23	54	15.00 (10.00-16.00)	9.255	.010*	26/27
	24-25	225	14.00 (11.00-17.00)			24/25
	26-27	148	11.00 (10.00-15.00)			
Positive Energy	22-23	54	17.00 (10.00-13.00)	6.298	.043*	22/23 24/25
	24-25	225	16.00 (11.00-15.00)			
	26-27	148	14.00 (08.00-14.00)			
Attitude Control	22-23	54	12.00 (11.00-14.00)	22.697	.000*	26/27
	24-25	225	11.00 (10.00-15.00)			24/25
	26-27	148	13.00 (11.00-16.00)			22/23 24/25
Psychological performance Total	22-23	54	100.00(91.00-115.50)	16.432	.000*	24/25
	24-25	225	109.00(87.00-117.00)			26/27
	26-27	148	91.00 (81.00-116.00)			

p < 0.005 *

When Table 4 is examined, there is a significant difference between the age group of 26-27 years and the age group of 24-25 years in the sub-dimension of self-esteem when assessing the psychological performances of the participants according to their ages. In the attention control sub-dimension, significant differences were found between the ages of 24-25 years and 26-27 years, and between 24-25 and 22-23 age groups. In the sub-dimension of motivation level, a significant difference was found between 24-25 age group and 26-27 age group. In terms of positive energy, it was calculated that there is a significant difference between 22-23 age group and 24-25 age group. In the attitude control subscale, significant differences were found between 24-25 age group and 22-23 and 26-27 age groups. There are significant differences between the ages of 24-25 years and 26-27 years in terms of total psychological performance. On the other hand, negative energy and visualization sub-dimensions do not appear to represent a significant difference in terms of age variable.

Table 5: Evaluation of Participants by Educational Status of Mother

	Educational Status of Mother	N	Median (25-75)	X²	p	U
Self-confidence	Secondary School	203	13.00 (09.00-16.00)	7.865	.049	-
	High School	127	14.00 (11.00-19.00)			
	Associate degree	62	12.00 (10.00-16.00)			
	University	35	12.00 (10.00-16.00)			
Negative Energy	Secondary School	203	16.00 (14.00-19.00)	3.702	.295	-
	High School	127	17.00 (13.00-20.00)			
	Associate degree	62	15.00 (13.00-18.00)			
	University	35	16.00 (14.00-20.00)			
Attention Control	Secondary School	203	17.00 (15.00-19.00)	10.334	.016*	High School/ Secondary School
	High School	127	18.00 (15.00-20.00)			
	Associate degree	62	16.00 (14.00-19.00)			
	University	35	16.00 (14.00-19.00)			
Visualization	Secondary School	203	13.00 (10.00-16.00)	4.955	.175	-
	High School	127	14.00 (10.00-17.00)			
	Associate degree	62	15.00 (11.00-17.00)			
	University	35	12.00 (11.00-16.00)			
Motivation Level	Secondary School	203	13.00 (10.00-16.00)	.590	.899	-
	High School	127	13.00 (10.00-16.00)			
	Associate degree	62	12.50 (10.00-16.00)			
	University	35	13.00 (10.00-15.00)			
Positive Energy	Secondary School	203	15.00 (12.00-17.00)	6.507	.089	-
	High School	127	16.00 (13.00-18.00)			
	Associate degree	62	14.50 (12.00-17.00)			
	University	35	15.00 (12.00-17.00)			
Attitude Control	Secondary School	203	12.00 (09.00-15.00)	4.737	.192	-
	High School	127	13.00 (10.00-15.00)			
	Associate degree	62	12.50 (10.00-15.00)			
	University	35	12.00 (09.00-14.00)			
Psychological performance Total	Secondary School	203	100.00 (85.00-116.00)	4.736	.192	-
	High School	127	104.00 (87.00-119.00)			
	Associate degree	62	100.00 (87.00-116.00)			
	University	35	95.00 (85.00-111.00)			

p < 0.005 *

According to Table 5, there is a significant difference between high school graduates and secondary school graduates in terms of mother's educational status in the Attention control sub-dimension. On the other hand, there is no significant difference in any of the self-confidence, negative energy, visualization, motivation level, positive energy, attitude control sub-dimensions regarding the mother's educational status variable. There was also no significant difference between the total score of psychological performance and mother's educational status variable.

Table 6: Evaluation of Participants' Psychological Performances according to the Educational Status of the Father

	Educational Status of Father	N	Median (25-75)	X²	p	U
Self-confidence	Secondary School	176	12.50 (10.00-16.00)	16.968	.001*	High School/ Secondary School
	High School	166	13.00 (12.00-17.00)			
	Associate degree	49	13.00 (9.00-19.00)			
	University	36	12.00 (9.00-19.00)			
Negative Energy	Secondary School	176	15.00 (14.00-19.00)	3.949	.267	-
	High School	166	17.00 (13.00-18.25)			
	Associate degree	49	17.00 (13.00-21.00)			
	University	36	16.00 (14.00-18.75)			
Attention Control	Secondary School	176	17.00 (15.00-19.00)	3.750	.290	-
	High School	166	14.00 (15.00-20.00)			
	Associate degree	49	18.00 (15.00-19.00)			
	University	36	16.50 (14.25-18.00)			
Visualization	Secondary School	176	15.00 (10.00-16.00)	6.893	.075	-
	High School	166	14.00 (11.00-16.25)			
	Associate degree	49	15.00 (10.00-16.00)			
	University	36	13.50 (10.00-17.00)			
Motivation Level	Secondary School	176	13.00 (11.00-16.00)	5.541	.136	-
	High School	166	14.00 (10.00-16.00)			
	Associate degree	49	14.00 (11.00-17.00)			
	University	36	11.50 (9.00-15.00)			
Positive Energy	Secondary School	176	14.00 (12.00-17.00)	7.648	.054	-
	High School	166	16.00 (12.00-15.00)			
	Associate degree	49	15.00 (13.50-18.00)			
	University	36	15.00 (11.25-18.00)			
Attitude Control	Secondary School	176	12.00 (12.50-16.00)	4.846	.183	-
	High School	166	12.00 (14.00-15.50)			
	Associate degree	49	14.00 (13.00-17.00)			
	University	36	15.00 (10.25-16.00)			
Psychological performance Total	Secondary School	176	96.00 (81.00-116.00)	3.420	.331	-
	High School	166	101.00(87.00-116.00)			
	Associate degree	49	104.00 (84.50-129.00)			
	University	36	102.00 (77.25-117.25)			

p < 0.005 *

When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that there is no significant difference between sub-dimensions of negative energy, attention control, visualization, motivation level, positive energy, attitude control sub-dimensions while there is a significant difference between secondary school graduates and high school graduates in the participants' fathers' educational status variable and self-confidence sub-dimension. On the other hand, there was no significant difference between the total score of psychological performance and the educational status of the father.

Table 7: Evaluation of Participants' Psychological Performances regarding their Departments

	Department	N	Median (25-75)	X ²	p	U
Self-confidence	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	15.00 (12.00-16.00)	16.331	.060	-
	Education	65	13.00 (10.00-17.00)			
	Economics and Administrative Sciences	52	12.00 (10.25-13.00)			
	Faculty of Science	33	11.00 (10.50-20.00)			
	Literature	50	12.00 (10.00-15.00)			
	Applied Sciences	21	12.00 (12.00-25.00)			
	Health Sciences	35	13.00 (13.00-15.00)			
	Theology	45	12.00 (10.50-16.50)			
	Engineering	50	14.00 (11.00-20.00)			
	Communication	39	10.00 (10.00-19.00)			
Negative Energy	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	18.00 (16.00-20.00)	47.049	.000*	Communication / Literature
	Education	65	16.00 (15.00-20.00)			Communication / Health
	Economics and Administrative Sciences	52	16.00 (13.00-18.00)			Communication / Education
	Faculty of Science	33	14.00 (11.50-19.00)			Communication / Applied
	Literature	50	17.00 (12.00-16.00)			Communication / Physical education
	Applied Sciences	21	20.00 (13.00-19.00)			Science / Education
	Health Sciences	35	17.00 (14.00-18.00)			Science / Applied
	Theology	45	16.00 (15.00-20.00)			Engineering / Physical education
	Engineering	50	15.50 (17.00-20.00)			
	Communication	39	14.00 (16.00-20.00)			
Attention Control	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	20.00 (12.00-19.00)	43.931	.000*	Literature / Physical education
	Education	65	17.00 (11.50-18.00)			
	Economics and Administrative Sciences	33	18.00 (13.00-20.00)			
	Faculty of Science	50	15.00 (16.00-20.00)			
	Literature	21	16.00 (15.00-20.00)			
	Applied Sciences	35	16.00 (12.50-19.50)			
	Health Sciences	45	16.00 (16.00-20.00)			
	Theology	39	18.00 (12.00-16.00)			
	Engineering		18.00 (16.50-20.00)			
	Communication		16.00 (14.00-17.00)			
Visualization	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	14.00 (15.00-19.00)	17.765	.038	-
	Education	65	15.00 (16.00-22.00)			
	Economics and Administrative Sciences	52	11.00 (12.00-20.00)			
	Faculty of Science	33	14.00 (14.00-19.00)			
	Literature	50	13.00 (15.00-20.00)			
	Applied Sciences	21	15.00 (14.50-19.00)			
	Health Sciences	35	12.00 (16.00-21.00)			
	Theology	45	13.00 (15.00-18.00)			
	Engineering	50	15.00 (11.50-17.25)			
	Communication	39	11.00 (16.00-19.00)			
	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	12.00 (11.00-20.00)			FEAS / Education
	Education	65	16.00 (13.00-22.00)			FEAS / Applied Theology /

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Motivation Level	Economics and Administrative Sciences	52	10.00 (15.00-20.00)	32.128	.000*	Education
	Faculty of Science	33	14.00 (16.00-19.00)			
	Literature	50	13.00 (11.00-21.00)			
	Applied Sciences	21	14.00 (13.00-17.00)			
	Health Sciences	35	13.00 (11.00-20.00)			
	Theology	45	11.00 (12.50-19.50)			
	Engineering	50	14.00 (16.00-18.25)			
	Communication	39	13.00 (9.00-20.00)			
Positive Energy	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	17.00 (11.00-18.00)	26.404	.002*	Physical education / FEAS Physical Education / Communication
	Education	65	16.00 (12.00-21.00)			
	Economics and Administrative Sciences	52	14.00 (13.00-22.00)			
	Faculty of Science	33	15.00 (10.00-21.00)			
	Literature	50	15.00 (10.50-17.00)			
	Applied Sciences	21	15.00 (11.00-18.00)			
	Health Sciences	35	14.00 (11.50-19.50)			
	Theology	45	14.00 (12.00-20.00)			
Attitude Control	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	14.00 (11.00-17.50)	34.495	.000*	Physical education / FEAS Physical Education / Theology Physical education / Communication Physical Education / Education Physical education / Edebyat
	Education	65	12.00 (11.00-18.00)			
	Economics and Administrative Sciences	52	10.00 (12.00-20.00)			
	Faculty of Science	33	14.00 (12.00-21.00)			
	Literature	50	12.00 (10.00-22.00)			
	Applied Sciences	21	14.00 (12.00-20.00)			
	Health Sciences	35	12.00 (9.00-16.50)			
	Theology	45	11.00 (11.00-19.00)			
Psychological performance Total	School of Physical Education and Sports	41	104.00 (98.00-104.00)	33.118	.000	Physical education / FEAS Physical education / Communication Physical Education / Theology
	Education	65	108.00 (92.00-119.00)			
	Economics and Administrative Sciences	52	90.00 (79.50-117.50)			
	Faculty of Science	33	91.00 (79.50-117.00)			
	Literature	50	100.00 (87.75-107.00)			
	Applied Sciences	21	110.00 (93.00-146.00)			
	Health Sciences	35	100.00 (85.00-106.00)			
	Theology	45	90.00 (85.00-119.50)			
Engineering	50	110.00 (78.00-117.00)				
Communication	39	91.00 (78.00-111.00)				

p < 0.005 *

When Table 7 is examined, it is seen that there is no significant difference between the self-confidence sub-dimension and the graduated departments. Significant differences were found between communication faculty and literature, health sciences, education, applied sciences faculty and physical education and sports school in terms of negative energy sub-dimension. It has also been found that there is a significant difference

between the faculty of science and the faculty of education and applied sciences. It is also seen that there is a significant difference between the engineering faculty and the physical education and sports school. In the sub-dimension of attention control, it is calculated that there is a significant difference between the faculty of literature and physical education and theology. In addition, there were significant differences between physical education and physics, communication, and health sciences. In the sub-dimension of motivation level, it was determined that there are significant differences between FEAS and education and applied sciences. When the positive energy sub-dimension was analyzed, a significant difference was found between physical education and the FEAS and Communication faculties. When the sub-dimension of attitude control was examined, significant differences were found between physical education and FEAS, theology, communication, education, and literature faculties. Finally, when the graduated departments and the total scores of psychological performance were examined, it was found that there was a significant difference between physical education and FEAS, theology and communication faculties.

Table 8: Evaluation of Participants' Psychological Performances according to their Residence Addresses

	Residence	N	Median (25-75)	X ²	p	U
Self-confidence	Town	18	15.00 (8.00-15.00)	9.139	.027	Metropolis-District
	Province	171	12.00 (9.00-18.00)			
	District	46	11.00 (6.00-16.00)			
	Metropolis	192	13.00 (10.00-16.75)			
Negative Energy	Town	18	15.50 (15.00-16.00)	7.627	.054	-
	Province	171	16.00 (14.00-20.00)			
	District	46	15.00 (13.00-17.00)			
	Metropolis	192	17.00 (13.00-20.00)			
Attention Control	Town	18	20.00 (14.00-20.50)	5.499	.139	-
	Province	171	17.00 (14.00-19.00)			
	District	46	17.00 (14.00-18.00)			
	Metropolis	192	17.00 (15.00-19.00)			
Visualization	Town	18	10.00 (10.00-14.25)	52.422	.000*	Province-District Metropolis-District Metropolis-Town
	Province	171	14.00 (11.00-16.00)			
	District	46	10.00 (7.50-11.00)			
	Metropolis	192	15.00 (10.00-17.00)			
Motivation Level	Town	18	10.00 (10.00-12.50)	25.312	.000*	Province-District Metropolis-District Metropolis-Town
	Province	171	13.00 (10.00-17.00)			
	District	46	9.00 (6.75-16.00)			
	Metropolis	192	13.00 (12.00-16.00)			
Positive Energy	Town	18	13.50 (12.00-14.00)	33.095	.000*	Metropolis-District Province-District
	Province	171	15.00 (14.00-18.00)			
	District	46	13.00 (10.00-13.00)			
	Metropolis	192	16.00 (12.00-18.00)			
Attitude Control	Town	18	10.00 (10.00-13.00)	28.597	.000*	Province-District Metropolis-District Metropolis-Town Metropolis-Province
	Province	171	12.00 (8.00-15.00)			
	District	46	10.00 (8.00-14.00)			
	Metropolis	192	13.00 (11.00-15.00)			
Psychological performance Total	Town	18	96.00 (81.00-99.50)	29.953	.000*	Metropolis-Province Province-District
	Province	171	100.00 (79.00-119.00)			
	District	46	84.00 (65.75- 106.00)			
	Metropolis	192	106.50 (89.75-117.00)			

p < 0.005 *

When Table 8 is examined, in terms of residence address variable, a significant difference was calculated between the metropolis and the district in the sub-dimension of self-confidence, between the province and the district and between the metropolis and the district and town for the visualization sub-dimension, between province and district and between district and town in motivation sub-dimension. In addition, a significant difference was found in the positive energy sub-dimension between metropolis and district and between province and district; and between province and district, metropolis and town in attitude control sub-dimension. When the total scores of the psychological performance were examined, a significant difference was found between province and metropolis and district.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

As well as physical performance, being psychologically robust is also crucial in policing profession. As a matter of course, it is inevitable to face psychologically difficult situations and it has been considered that psychological performance has been becoming remarkable. In this study, it has been determined that there is no significant difference between the gender variables and psychological performances of the participants of the study in any of the sub-dimensions. No significant difference has been found between genders in terms of psychological performance in the study on adolescents carried out by Yöndem and Bahtiyar (2016). In the study conducted by Sucan (2012) with athletes, the psychological performance parameters between the genders are not significant. Hori (2010) and Kirkcoldy, Furnham, and Siefen (2010) have carried out studies showing that the psychological well-being does not differ according to gender. It has been considered that due to the increasing significance attributed to the education of women, the increase in the number of women in the working life and the increase in the number of literacy and equal rate of participation in higher education with men, the psychological performance of women might have become similar to the psychological performance of men.

In evaluation of psychological performance considering age, there have been significant differences between 24-25 and 26-27 years of age. Psychological performance score between 24 and 25 years has been found as higher than other age groups. Significant differences have also been found in the sub-dimensions such as self-confidence, attention control, motivation level, positive attitude and attitude control. In Chan's (2003) study on the correlation between psychological performance and age, it has been found that the primary effect of the age variable on teachers' psychological performance dimensions is not significant. Sezgin's (2009) study did not find a significant relationship between the age of the teachers and their levels of psychological performance. When the literature is examined, it may be seen that there are also researches which include studies suggesting that psychological performance is related to age. For instance, Hannah and Morrissey (1986) – in their study- have reported that a significant decrease in the level of girls' psychological endurance as they aged. In our study, it has been considered that the 24-25 age group is at the upper level of the

productivity period and that the idea of being employed and obtaining status by relying on the bachelor degree diploma increases the psychological performance in this age group due to the self-confidence.

When the correlation between psychological performance and educational status of mother is examined, a significant difference is not found, while a significant difference is only found in attention control sub-dimension. As it is the same in our study, Güngörmüş et al. (2015) have reported that there is no significant difference between educational status of mother and psychological performance in the department of nursing on the other hand, Sadioğlu and Bilgin (2008) have found that educational status of mother influences psychological performance as a result of their study focusing on primary school students. When our working group was examined, it has been determined that the participants have an average age of 25. It has been considered that participants in this age group who developed the independent viewpoint are not affected by the level of education of their mothers and instead it has been thought that they constituted their own mental structures independently.

When the correlation between psychological performance and educational status of father is examined, it has been found that there is no significant difference, while there was a significant difference only in self-confidence sub-dimension. In a study, it was found that children's psychology is influenced by the educational status of father. Harper (2010) has found that educational status of parents does not significantly affect the behaviors of the 7-19 age group. In our working group, it has been determined that educational status of father did not significantly affect psychological performance, since the average age is high and the participants are in the middle of their period of productivity.

When the participants are examined according to their graduated departments, it has been found that it significantly affected the psychological performance. It has been seen that participants who graduated from school of physical education and sports have higher psychological performance than the participants who graduated from the other departments. In the study of Demirtaş et al. (2011), it has been found out that the self-efficacy perceptions of physical education teachers are high. It was reported that physical education teachers gain more competence rather than individuals who graduated from the other departments, because of the fact that the curriculum in school of physical education and sports is basically applied and also these schools admit the students with applying skill tests; therefore these students have more chance to evaluate themselves.

Tepeköylü et al. (2009) have stated that the physical education departments have higher average scores for communication skills in their research, which consists of university students. It has been thought that prospective physical education teachers intensely use their communication skills and the positive effects of active life can be seen in their communication scores, as they get theoretical courses and applied classes at the same semesters during the education period. Besides, it is generally accepted that physical education and sports school students are superior to other departments' students in the race track test based on the physical performances applied on the

candidate students, although no relevant work is found in the literature. This general acceptance is thought to be due to the use of similar tests when accepting students to physical education and sports schools, the students' having a sporting background and the applied courses are widely included in the curriculum

Significant differences have been found regarding psychological performance when the participants are examined according to their residence addresses. When the total score of psychological performance is examined, there is an increase in psychological performance scores as the residences are enlarged. The average score of the volunteers living in the metropolises is higher than the participants live in other places. Akten (1999) has found higher levels of self-acceptance for the high school students who spent most of their lives in the bigger cities/metropolises than those who spent most of their lives in towns, villages and smaller cities. According to the findings of study Ünal (2016), the metropolises positively affect the individuals living there in terms of technology, sports, culture and art, employment, education and health facilities. It has been considered in our study that there are significant differences in favor of the metropolises because of the existence of various educational institutions in the big centers, the excess social opportunities, the intense interaction, the existence of sports and cultural activities and the ease of accessing many services.

In this study, according to certain variables, the psychological performance of prospective polices varies according to age, the departments that they graduated from and their place of residence, regardless of gender and educational status of their parents. As a result, it is thought that considering the psychological performances of candidates preparing for sports tests of police vocational training centers will contribute to making a healthier selection. The profession of policing is a profession in which physical endurance, psychological endurance, and performance are the forerunners. For this reason, in addition to sports tests, policing training centers should also consider studies addressing the psychological performance and the mental field.

4.1 Limitations

- Since the study is conducted in Kayseri province, regional factors can be effective, so that, if tests could be applied in different cities in different regions, the universe would be better reflected
- More variables on participants' psychological performance can be emphasized
- Psychological performances of incumbent policemen can be measured and included in the study, or psychological fieldwork can be added according to the area of expertise of the police.
- The duration of the study can be extended and the study can be re-performed at different intervals

4.2 Suggestions

- For the police profession, psychological performance tests as well as PPSE and sports tests can be applied.

- Psychological performance of applicants during sports tests can be determined, and thus, the results can be compared to those who already have a career in this profession.
- This study can be applied to present police officers to increase their psychological performance through in-service trainings and also low psychological performance can be increased by means of this implementation.
- Tests and trainings should be periodically repeated according to the units that the police officers will serve (terrorism, narcotics, public order, organized crime etc.).

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